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Effect of Double Annealing on the Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of a Medium Manganese Steel

Mattia Franceschi¹ | Jose A. Jimenez¹ | Carlos Garcia-Mateo¹ | Radhakanta Rana²

¹MATERIALIA-Steel Research Group, Department of Physical Metallurgy, National Centre for Metallurgical Research (CENIM-CSIC), Madrid, Spain |

²Tata Steel Europe Ltd., IJmuiden, Netherlands

Correspondence: Mattia Franceschi (m.franceschi@cenim.csic.es)

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the evolution of microstructure and mechanical behavior in medium manganese steel subjected to double intercritical annealing was investigated. Austenite reversion transformation (ART) occurred during both single (730°C) and double intercritical annealing (700°C and 750°C). A complex ultrafine microstructure consisting of three phases—retained austenite, martensite, and ferrite—with fine carbides was formed after single annealing. Following double annealing at 700°C, the martensite generated during the first intercritical annealing reverted to austenite, resulting in the maximum stabilized austenite fraction and a final microstructure composed mainly of ferrite and retained austenite. When the second annealing temperature was increased to 750°C, a larger amount of austenite was formed; however, its reduced thermal stability caused partial transformation into martensite. Double intercritical annealing thus produced multiple populations of austenite and ferrite/martensite phases with varying thermal and mechanical stabilities, enhancing the overall mechanical performance. The strength was maximized after high-temperature (750°C) double annealing, whereas elongation and ductility were optimized at the lower annealing temperature (700°C).

1 | Introduction

Nowadays, due to the latest regulations to reduce fuel consumption and the emission of greenhouse gas, car makers are involved in the development of lightweight, strong automotive structures, while preserving the safety of the passenger [1–6]. Although promising aluminum alloys with enhanced properties have been developed [7, 8], steels are the fundament in this sector [9–11], due to the superior mechanical properties, formability, lower costs, and easier recyclability [12]. A significant evolution occurred in the last decades in the automotive steels, the third-generation advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) presents a carefully engineered balance of strength, ductility, and economic feasibility, positioning them as key materials for advanced lightweight automotive structures [13, 14]. Among the steels considered as the 3rd generation of AHSS, medium manganese steels (MMnS) containing approximately 3–12 wt.% Mn have emerged as promising candidates for lightweight safer car-body components [15], including

structural parts, bumper systems, doors, and other safety components [12], owing to their superior strength–ductility synergy and formability [16–21] compared to the first-generation AHSS and the lower cost compared to the second generation AHSS [22].

Medium Mn steels typically exhibit ultimate tensile strengths (UTS) in the range of 800–2000 MPa, total elongations (TEL) of 15%–60% (in some cases up to 80% [23]), and product of strength and elongation (PSE) in the range 25 000–70 000 MPa% [23–26]. This is further complemented by a remarkable impact toughness, which is a fundamental requirement for materials used in the automotive sector in order to meet safety standards and improve crash-worthiness [27]. Typically, the MMnS are characterized by a duplex or triplex microstructure consisting of: (i) ferrite (α), (ii) carbon enriched retained austenite (RA, γ , 5–30 vol.%) [28–30] which, under deformation can transform into martensite [6, 31] giving transformation induced plasticity (TRIP) effect and/or exhibit twinning-induced plasticity (TWIP) effect [1],

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(iii) and/or fresh martensite (α') formed during final room temperature cooling [25].

As highlighted in several reviews on the topic [22, 32], the development of MMnS requires a comprehensive understanding of the effects of alloying elements, thermomechanical processing, heat treatments and the relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties, partly because a considerable amount of RA with tailored stability is a key factor for the performance of the MMnS steels. Concerning the heat treatments, several studies focused on the investigation of the microstructural evolution and mechanical response during single intercritical annealing treatments [33], based on the austenite reversion concept [34–36], since it allows for a simple control of the process and allows for stabilizing large amount of austenite (up to 50%) [33]. These studies attempted at clarifying the effects of various parameter such as annealing temperature [37–40], annealing time [24, 37, 41–44], and heating and cooling rates [24, 45] of single annealing. However, recent publications have demonstrated that the mechanical properties of medium Mn steels can be significantly enhanced through a double annealing process, also called two-step annealing [46] or double soaking [30]. Double annealing is an advanced processing strategy that involves the application of a second intercritical annealing step, devoted to increase the available volume fraction of stable austenite. It can be carried out either at lower [25, 47] or higher temperatures [30] compared to the first annealing step and leads to develop a microstructure consisting of a small fraction of proeutectoid ferrite and a fine and dispersed mixture of martensite and austenite. As proposed by Glover et al. [30], the first soaking in the intercritical region promotes the stabilization of a considerable fraction of austenite (γ) due to carbon and manganese partitioning. However, depending on the soaking temperature and on the extent of the austenite reversion process, some athermal fresh martensite (α') may still form upon cooling to room temperature, which can adversely affect the mechanical behavior. In this framework, the second annealing stage becomes essential: during this treatment, previously formed martensite is partially replaced by ferrite (α) within the matrix because of the tempering reaction and partially reverts to austenite, while previously formed austenite is maintained in the microstructure. Again, part of the newly formed austenite may transform to martensite upon cooling when annealing is performed at high temperatures.

Therefore, after a double annealing treatment, the medium Mn steel microstructure consists of a small fraction of α with a mix of α' and fine-dispersed γ . Moreover, if present in the microstructure, α' is characterized also a by a twofold morphology, e.g., laths and small nonetching blocks, that can be associated with different degrees of C and Mn partitioning generated by a double soaking [45]. According to Kozłowska et al. [45], due to the multiple reheating and the development of regions with different carbon enrichment, there are areas with low C and Mn content transforms into martensite at high temperatures (α'_1) upon the final cooling, while the richer regions transform at lower temperatures (α'_2). α'_1 shows a lath type morphology, while α'_2 appears as blocks (typically unetched). The α'_2 phase, being characterized by high carbon and manganese, exhibits higher hardness compared to α'_1 ; however, the presence of α'_2 and α'_1 martensite must be balanced, because a large amount of hard martensite affects negatively the mechanical properties, since hard regions can act as stress concentrators and potential void and crack initiation sites.

Furthermore, during double annealing, the microstructure is also affected by the duration of the second stage, the cooling rates, and the presence of cementite. As reported by the same authors, in Ref. [45], on one hand, manganese reduces the dissolution of cementite, the duration of the heat treatment should be calibrated to make carbon available for austenite. In case of incomplete dissolution of cementite, the C/Mn content in RA formed at ferrite–cementite interface is higher than in austenite formed at ferrite grain boundaries; therefore, it is natural to assume that austenite populations characterized by different stability are present in the microstructure [48].

Ye et al. [25] observed that after a double annealing, carried out at different temperatures (600°C–640°C), of a Fe–0.5C–7 Mn (wt.%) steel, a bimodal-grained austenite forms due to the double austenite reversion and the ferrite coarsening, resulting in a general improvement of the mechanical properties. Han et al. [49] observed that the development of bimodal microstructure caused the acceleration of the Lüders bands propagation and the suppression of the local plastic instability phenomena. Furthermore, Xu et al. [50] demonstrated that during double annealing, a higher enrichment of manganese and carbon is achieved, which coupled with a mixture of coarse and ultrafine austenite, leads to a 27 % increase of the tensile strength (from 752–954 MPa), while maintaining an adequate ductility (from 52.7 % to 39.2 %). The optimization of the mechanical properties was also achieved by promoting the formation of austenitic grains with gradients in the manganese concentration and introducing θ -particles (during an intermediate tempering stage) which act as nucleation sites during the reversion stage [51].

The creation of a bimodal structure in a two-step annealing can activate ductility-enhancing mechanisms other than the TRIP effect. According to Lee and coauthors [52], the formation of ultrafine austenite induces a change in the deformation mechanism of austenite from TRIP to the TWIP mechanism. In particular, the authors observed in a Fe–0.26C–10.1Mn–6.41Al (wt.%) alloy that TRIP phenomenon occurred primarily in coarse γ grains, while in austenite grains with a size smaller than 10 μm the TWIP mechanism prevailed.

Considering the scope of developing steels for the automotive industry, it is important to consider the compatibility of the investigated thermal processing and the galvanizing treatment used in industry because it provides the required corrosion resistance. In this regard, most of the work in literature is devoted to understanding the corrosion properties and the coating quality of medium Mn steels [53, 54], while ignoring the phase transformation and its compatibility with galvanizing. Also, the processing involving galvanizing and the final microstructure and properties of these steels are rarely reported. Moreover, many medium Mn steels that were developed to guarantee sufficient mechanical properties were characterized by heat treatments incompatible with the processing via continuous galvanizing line (CGL) [55–57]. Therefore, this study aims at further exploring intercritical annealing coupled with hot-dip galvanizing treatment, followed by a second annealing, on the microstructure and mechanical properties of a MMnS for the automotive industry.

2 | Materials and Methods

The material investigated in this study is a low-carbon 5.02 wt.% Mn containing cold rolled MMnS containing minor additions of

Al, Si, Cr, and V. Total impurity content was below 0.05 wt.% Vacuum induction melting and casting, using electrolytic iron (99.99% purity) and various ferroalloys for alloying additions, were employed to produce a 25 kg ingot. The ingot was reheated at 1200°C, hot-rolled to a thickness of 3 mm, with a finish rolling temperature above 930°C and microstructure and coiled. Then hot-rolled strips were subjected to a softening annealing at 600°C, to obtain a ferrite/austenite microstructure. Finally, the material was cold rolled to a final thickness of 1.5 mm, giving 50% reduction. In order to determine the critical transformation temperatures of austenite start, austenite finish and martensite start (A_{c1} , A_{c3} , M_s respectively), the cold rolled steel was heated to 650°C at 10°C/s, then further heated up to 900°C at 1°C/s, held for 5 min and finally quenched at 50°C/s to room temperature in a Bahr 805A (TA Instruments, Hull, Germany) high-resolution quenching dilatometer. The dilatometer also recorded any phase transformations that occurred during the thermal cycles by measuring the relative change in length (RCL) of the specimen. Heating in the dilatometer was done by an induction coil, while helium was used for cooling. The specimen temperature was constantly monitored with a K-type thermocouple spot-welded on the sample surface at the mid length. Flat specimens measuring 10 mm in length, 5 mm in width, and 1.5 mm in thickness were used for this purpose. Fused silica push-rods, in contact with the samples, with a thermal expansion coefficient of $0.54 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and a linear variable differential transducer (LVDT) were used to record the length variations [58–60]. Based on the experimentally determined A_{c1} and A_{c3} , details provided in a later section, the first intercritical annealing treatment was carried out at 730°C for 64 s, cooled to 470°C and isothermally held for 72 s and then finally cooled to room temperature, as shown schematically in Figure 1. The isothermal holding at 470°C is the simulation of the hot-dip galvanizing (GI) step in a continuous annealing (CA) line, necessary for having a zinc-based coating on the steel surface. This entire treatment corresponds to the simulation of CA. The sample with the first annealing and galvanizing is identified as CA-730. A second intercritical annealing was also performed as described in Figure 1, at 700°C and 750°C for 3 min. The heat treatments were performed in the same dilatometric equipment. The samples subjected to the double annealing are called CA-730–700 and CA-730–750, respectively. All the annealing simulations were conducted under the protective atmosphere of helium.

The identification and evolution of the microstructural constituents after the various heat treatments were done by means of

FIGURE 1 | Schematic diagram of the double annealing process.

observations in a field emission gun scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM), FEI-QUANTA 250 (Quanta-FEI Eindhoven, Netherland), operating at 20 kV. The FEG-SEM is equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscope (EDS) detector (UltraDry, Thermo Scientific) coupled with Pathfinder Software. Specimens were prepared following the standard metallographic procedures, which included grinding with SiC papers (from 180–2400 grit) and subsequent polishing with 6, 3, and 1 μm polycrystalline diamond pastes. Finally, the microstructure was revealed using a 3% Nital etching solution. Multiple etching-polishing cycles were performed in order to remove the deformed layer induced by mechanical grinding, thus improving the definition of the microstructural characteristics and eliminating any martensite that could have formed from austenite due to the TRIP effect. All the observations were carried out on the thickness plane of the specimens, along the rolling direction (i.e., the plane of rolling direction and normal direction, RD-ND plane).

The volume fractions of RA (V_γ) and ferrite/martensite (V_α) at room temperature were quantified from X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns acquired using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with Co – $K\alpha$ radiation, a Göbel mirror, and a LynxEye position-sensitive detector. Measurements were performed in coupled θ – 2θ mode over the 2θ range of 35°–135°, with a step size of 0.015° and a counting time of 2 s per step, under tube settings of 40 kV voltage and 30 mA current. For the XRD measurement, the specimens were further polished with OP-U silica suspension with 40 nm particle size.

Phase quantification was conducted via Rietveld refinement using TOPAS v4.2 (Bruker AXS) software, with a crystallographic model incorporating standard structure data for ferrite and austenite. Refined parameters included lattice constants, scale factors, background, and two-theta offset. As crystallographic texture can significantly influence peak intensities in steels, the texture effect was corrected using the generalized spherical harmonics model, without recourse to pole figure data. Carbon contents in austenite (C_γ) was estimated from the refined lattice parameters, using empirical correlations in Equation (1) [61, 62].

$$\begin{aligned} a\gamma = & 3.573 + 0.0453 \text{ C} + 0.00095 \text{ Mn} + 0.0056 \text{ Al} + 0.0006 \text{ Cr} \\ & + 0.00157 \text{ Si} - 0.0002 \text{ Ni} + 0.0039 \text{ Ti} + 0.0018 \text{ V} \\ & + 0.0220 \text{ N} - 0.0004 \text{ Co} + 0.0015 \text{ Cu} + 0.0031 \text{ Mo} \\ & + 0.0051 \text{ Nb} + 0.0018 \text{ W} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

all in wt.%.

Vickers microhardness measurements at 1 kgf load (HV1) were carried out on the RD-ND plane, and the reported values represent the average of at least five independent indentations in the mid-thickness. Dog bone-shaped tensile specimens were extracted by means of wire electro discharge machining (EDM) from the dilatometric samples, with a gauge length of 2.5 mm (parallel length of 4 mm) and a width of 2 mm. Tensile tests were conducted at a quasistatic strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, with in a tensile testing machine with 10 kN tensile testing load cell machine (ZwickRoell, model DO730054Z010). Strain was recorded with a laser extensometer (Messphysik LaserXtens). At least two tests were performed per condition. After the tests, the fracture mechanism was investigated by SEM analysis of the fracture surface.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Initial Microstructure

Figure 2 displays the microstructure of the steel in the cold-rolled state. The SEM micrograph shows that the microstructure is essentially martensitic (α'), while RA (γ) was not observed and not even detected in XRD, probably due to the low volume fraction, below the detection limit ($\sim 3\%$) and/or its small size [63]. Moreover, it must be considered that after hot rolling, owing to the high hardenability of the medium Mn steel and the absent C or Mn enrichment, upon cooling to room temperature, γ mainly transforms into martensite. While upon cold rolling, the remaining fraction of austenite exhibits the TRIP effect, leading to an essentially martensitic structure by further reduction in the γ volume fraction. The measured hardness in the cold rolled condition was 363 ± 6 HV1.

3.2 | Heat Treatment Design

Dilatometric tests were conducted to measure the RCL while heating the cold-rolled microstructures from room temperature to the

FIGURE 2 | Initial microstructure in cold-rolled condition consisting of martensite (α').

FIGURE 3 | (a) Temperature versus RCL curve showing the experimentally determined A_{c1} , A_{c3} , M_s . (b) Temperature versus austenite volume fraction curve derived by the lever rule.

fully austenitic field, 900°C . Applying the intercept method, A_{c1} , A_{c3} , M_s were found to be 690°C , 825°C , and 325°C , respectively (Figure 3a). Based on the dilatometric curves obtained from the fully austenitized sample, Figure 3a, the lever rule was applied following Ref. [64] to determine the evolution of the austenite volume fraction as a function of the intercritical temperature, as shown in Figure 3b. As it is evident, for the first annealing step, at a temperature of 730°C , an austenite volume fraction of 16% is expected after reheating.

3.3 | Phase Transformation Studies

The phase transformation occurring during double annealing was rationalized with the support of dilatometry. Figure 4 shows the dilatometric data acquired during the first annealing. Thus, during heating (Figure 4a), the material shows a linear thermal expansion, with a slight deviation in the slope related to the change in the heating rates, typical of the industrial process adopted in this study. As shown in Figure 4b, from 690°C (red square), the RCL exhibits a reduction in the net expansion rate, which reflects the competition between two effects: the thermal expansion associated with the temperature increase and the contraction induced by the austenite reversion and growth, in agreement with Ref [65]. The transformation of austenite continues during the isothermal stage, as shown by Martin et al. [34], and in fact, the specimen contraction commences almost immediately once the soaking starts at 730°C , without showing an incubation period (Figure 4c). The contraction observed in the RCL did not reach a plateau by the end of the 64 s holding period, indicating that the austenite reversion process was incomplete within this timeframe. Once the material was cooled down to the galvanizing temperature (i.e., 470°C), it contracted linearly without showing any visible transformation. Similarly, during the isothermal holding at 470°C , the material does not exhibit any phase transformation: just a slight expansion detected in the first seconds (Figure 4a), most certainly ascribed to the system settling and the noise of the measurements. The authors exclude that the bainitic transformation took place, since the

FIGURE 4 | Dilatometric results for the first annealing step: (a) temperature versus RCL curve for the whole annealing cycle, (b) detail of the temperature–RCL curve for the heating stage in the range 650°C–730°C, (c) time versus RCL curve relative to the isothermal stage at 730°C, and (d) temperature versus RCL curve relative to the final cooling to room temperature. The red square indicates the onset of the austenite reversion.

order of magnitude of such expansion is smaller compared to that of a conventional bainite formation [66].

During cooling from 470°C, Figure 4d, there was no phase change visible in the dilatometer signal until 83°C, where an expansion coherent with a martensitic transformation was detected. Thus, evidencing the fact that austenite carbon content, together with the partitioning of the substitutional alloying elements, especially manganese, was not sufficient to fully stabilize all the austenite during cooling to room temperature.

The dilatometric behavior of the investigated material during the second annealing is then illustrated in Figure 5. First, it was found that austenite reversion occurs during heating; however, the onset temperature of austenite reversion slightly decreases in the second annealing, to around 663°C. This behavior is attributed to the chemical heterogeneities generated during the first annealing, particularly along lath martensite boundaries, where regions locally enriched in Mn and C act as preferential nucleation sites and increase the driving force for reversion, thereby accelerating the transformation and shifting its start to lower temperatures [25, 67]. In addition, the presence of pre-existing austenite in the microstructure facilitates further reversion and growth during the second annealing, contributing to a higher austenite volume fraction, which may even exceed the equilibrium value [68].

Similarly, to the first annealing stage, the austenite reversion proceeded throughout the isothermal stage, exemplified with a contraction, from -0.035% to -0.103% for the CA-730–700 and CA-730–750 conditions, respectively see Figure 5b. As the isothermal holding temperature increases, the amount of

austenite increases. As in the case of the first annealing, the austenite reversion process is clearly unfinished at the end of the 3 min holding, since the curves in Figure 5b do not show a plateau. Furthermore, an increase in the kinetics of the transformation is observed as the second annealing temperature increases. The isothermal stage is followed, for both the annealing at 700°C and 750°C, by a linear contraction toward room temperature. Notably, annealing at 750°C leads to a clear martensitic transformation at approximately 178°C, whereas the 700°C treatment retains a linear RCL with no evident transformation, indicating the absence of martensite formation in the latter.

Sequential annealing at 750°C alters the austenite’s carbon content, making it poorer in carbon relative to the first annealing cycle. This shift causes the martensite start temperature (M_s) to increase and enhances the fraction of austenite that transforms to martensite upon cooling. The resultant transformation yields greater total expansion, i.e., RCL, signifying a more extensive austenite-to-martensite conversion.

3.4 | Microstructural Characterization

The microstructure after the first annealing step primarily consists of martensitic/austenitic (α'/γ) islands, resulting from the austenite reversion and the partial martensitic transformation occurring during cooling from the intercritical region to room temperature and a scarce amount of ferrite and dispersed cementite (Figure 6a). Moreover, as displayed in Figure 7, a compositional analysis of the intercritically annealed samples was carried out using the SEM-EDS technique. Considering the

FIGURE 5 | Dilatometric results for the second annealing step: (a) temperature versus RCL curve for the whole annealing cycle, (b) time versus RCL curve during the isothermal stage at 700°C and 750°C, and (c) temperature versus RCL curve during the final cooling to room temperature.

FIGURE 6 | SEM micrographs illustrating the microstructure of the single and double annealed specimens. (a) low and high magnification micrographs of the specimen subjected to the single annealing at 730°C, and (b) & (c) low and high magnification of the specimens subjected to double annealing at 700°C and 750°C, respectively, following the single annealing.

FIGURE 7 | Manganese concentration obtained from the EDS analysis of the specimen subjected to the single annealing at 730°C. The orange dashed line indicates the location of the acquisition of the spectrum.

low spatial resolution of the technique and the small size of the constituents, from the line scans, we could only infer a nonhomogeneous distribution of the Mn, showing some spikes corresponding to the α'/γ islands, as a result of the manganese partitioning occurring during the intercritical annealing.

After the first annealing step, once the material is subjected to a second annealing at 700°C, the final microstructure of the steel is a mixture of ferrite and austenite, with still some undissolved carbides (Figure 6b). It is worth noting that the ferritic phase in this case is the sum of the ferrite formed during the austenitization and

that resulting from the tempering of the previously formed martensite (occurred during heating of the second annealing). On the other hand, an increase in the annealing temperature (from 700°C–750°C) results in the dissolution of the majority of the cementite, and gives a mixture of ferrite and martensite/austenite regions, as confirmed by the SEM observations, shown in Figure 6c. It can be observed that the α/γ' regions present a two-fold morphology: first, a more globular shape, as highlighted in the red circles, which, according to Ye et al. [25], are obtained from the reverted transformation of α' martensite with active recrystallization. Moreover, as observed by Zhang et al. [69], globular reverted austenite grains preferentially nucleate and grow along prior austenite boundaries (PAGB) or the martensite packets, while the pre-existing ferrite or RA in the sample subjected to a single annealing further grows into coarse globular-shaped grains during second annealing. The other morphology of the α/γ' aggregate is the lath shape (inside light blue circles), which nucleated at the lath boundary and grew along the original laths, and these aggregates derive from an incomplete recrystallization of the previously formed martensite.

Figure 8 shows volume fractions of the RA determined by XRD analysis and the carbon contents deduced from the lattice parameters. In agreement with the dilatometric results, the volume fraction of RA increases during the second annealing at 700°C where a martensitic transformation was not detected. However, it decreases when the second soaking is carried out at 750°C. At a higher temperature (750°C), closer to the completion of the austenitization (e.g., A_{c3}), the amount of austenite is greater compared to at 700°C. Therefore, the intercritical austenite is insufficiently enriched in carbon and manganese, reducing its thermal stability and leading to an increase in M_s . It has been observed in Refs. [45, 70] that this introduction of martensite during second annealing, instead of soft ferrite, could also be beneficial to increase the strength properties of medium-Mn steels.

3.5 | Mechanical Behavior of Single and Double Annealed Samples

The hardness evolution after the first and second annealing is reported in Figure 9. First, it can be observed that both single and double annealing induce an increase in hardness compared to the as-received state. Moreover, the hardness evolution reflects the austenite volume fraction illustrated in Figure 8a. After the single annealing at 730°C, a first increase (366–428 HV1) in

FIGURE 9 | Hardness (HV1) evolution after single annealing (CA-730), and double annealing at 700°C (CA-730–700) and 750°C (CA-730–750).

observed due to the formation of fresh martensite after the austenite reversion; while after the second annealing at 700°C the newly formed martensite reverts to austenite, and is fully stabilized due to the further carbon, which reaches a maximum (Figure 8b), and manganese partitioning achieved by the second reheating, leading to a mixture of ferrite and austenite resulting in a reduced hardness (417 HV1). When the second annealing temperature is increased to 750°C, the extent of the austenite reversion is greater; however, due to the low carbon (Figure 8b) and manganese content, resulting in a martensitic matrix and the maximum value of 468 HV1.

Figure 10a–c present the representative engineering stress–strain curves of the single and double-annealed samples obtained from quasistatic tensile tests conducted at room temperature. The achieved mechanical properties for the three investigated conditions are summarized in Table 1. The sample CA-730 subjected to a single annealing exhibits continuous yielding behavior without yield point elongation (YPE = 0%), which is attributed to the high density of mobile dislocations present in the fresh martensitic structure [25]. The yield strength (YS) and UTS of this sample reached values of 631 and 1454 MPa respectively, while the uniform elongation (UE) and total elongation (TEL) were 10.0% and 11.5% respectively. The product of UTS and TE (PSE) attained a value of 16.7 GPa%, as summarized in Table 1.

Under double annealing, the mechanical properties of the CA-730–700 sample were markedly altered. The YS increased to

FIGURE 8 | (a) Retained austenite volume fraction and (b) carbon content of retained austenite (C_γ) of the single annealed (CA-730) and the double annealed samples (CA-730–700 and CA-730–750) determined by XRD. The carbon content was deduced from the lattice parameters.

FIGURE 10 | Tensile behavior of the single annealed (CA-730) and double annealed (CA-730–700 and CA-730–750) specimens. (a–c) representative engineering stress–strain curves, and (d–f) instantaneous work hardening curves.

TABLE 1 | Average tensile properties with the standard deviations of the single and double- annealed specimens.

Sample	YS,MPa	UTS,MPa	UE,%	TE,%	UTS × TE, 10 ³ MPa%
CA-730	631 ± 3	1454 ± 22	10.0 ± 0.5	11.5 ± 0.9	16.72
CA-730-700	647 ± 11	1265 ± 21	19.5 ± 0.3	37.6 ± 4.1	47.56
CA-730-750	911 ± 92	1617 ± 14	12.1 ± 0.1	13.3 ± 0.89	21.50

647 MPa, while the UTS decreased to 1265 MPa, but both uniform UE and TE increased to 19.5% and 37.6%, respectively, and PSE improved significantly, reaching 47.56 GPa%. It is to note that this is the best combination of strength and ductility, under the current experimental conditions, when the steel is subjected to two-step annealing. However, the tensile response of CA-730–700 sample is characterized by a pronounced but short discontinuous yielding phenomenon, featuring a distinct yield plateau (YPE ≈ 2.58 %). This behavior is associated with the propagation of Lüders bands, induced by localized deformation instability, which gives rise to measurable YPE, while no serrated plastic flow due to Portevin–Le Châtelier (PLC) effect was observed.

As the second annealing temperature was increased to 750°C, the YS of CA-730–750 sample further increased significantly to 911 MPa compared with that of CA-730–700 sample. The UTS also increased, reaching an ultrahigh level of 1617 MPa. However, the ductility deteriorated significantly, with the UE and TE decreasing to 12.1% and 13.3%, respectively. Nevertheless, even though the mechanical behavior of this sample appears to be

brittle, there is an improvement when compared to the single annealing, both in terms of strength and ductility, but only in strength if compared to the double annealing at 700°C, with a significant reduction of the ductility. The second annealing at an optimum temperature (i.e., 700°C) appears as an effective processing method to improve the strength and the ductility compared to the single annealed condition, because of the introduction of a new bct/bcc population [45], and the introduction of multiple populations of austenite, with different degree of stability that delays the fracture, as those shown in Figure 6 or reported in Ref. [71]. Moreover, the dissolution of the majority of cementite might also be beneficial in avoiding nucleation of cracks, thus retarding the initiation of instability. On the other hand, the 750°C double annealed sample exhibits a globally lower amount of less stable austenite (lowest C_γ in Figure 8), that clearly leads to poorer ductility.

To further elucidate the distinct mechanical characteristics of the single and double annealed specimens, their instantaneous work hardening behavior during deformation was examined, using the

change in the instantaneous work hardening exponent n , calculated on the basis of the Ratke and Welch equation (Equation (2)) [72, 73]:

$$n = \frac{d(\ln(\sigma))}{d(\ln(\epsilon))} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, σ is the true stress and ϵ is the true strain. The occurrence of macronecking was determined by the instability criterion of $n = \epsilon$.

The results are reported in Figure 10d,f. All the curves show a typical strain hardening peak at the beginning, followed by a continuous decrease as the strain increases, typical of TRIP-assisted steels [74, 75]. However, as shown also in the tensile curves, the three tested conditions display different evolutions of the instantaneous work hardening coefficient, whose interpretation is not straightforward considering the influence of multiple factors.

The first key aspect to consider is related to the variation in microstructural constituents—particularly the presence and volume fraction of martensite—as well as the mechanical stability of RA and its strain-induced transformation [76]. This transformation is itself influenced by several factors, including austenite size, morphology, the nature of the surrounding matrix [77] and, finally, the overall hardness.

In the martensite containing specimens (CA-730 and CA-730–750), which underwent single annealing and double annealing at 750°C, respectively, the value of n increases steeply compared to the martensite-free specimen CA-730–700. Among these, CA-730–750 shows a lower n value compared to CA-730 (0.15 and 0.26, respectively). After the double annealing at 750°C the volume fraction of martensite both at the expense of ferrite and austenite, and in agreement with Ref. [78], as the volume fraction of martensite increases, and consequently the hardness of the specimen, the overall work hardening during tensile loading decreases.

At this point, the influence of austenite and its response to the external loading must be taken into account. In particular, the surrounding matrix affects the stress and strain that austenite experiences at a certain stress/strain level. When embedded in a harder matrix (such as bainitic ferrite or martensite), austenite experiences lower local stress and strain compared to when it is surrounded by soft ferrite [77]. Therefore, due to a harder matrix (Figure 9), in the specimens CA-730 and CA-730–750, at the initial stage there is no contribution given by the austenite embedded in the microstructure, with the TRIP effect that is hindered. On the contrary, austenite significantly contributes at later stages, and this may explain the different decreasing trends observed among these specimens. Once austenite becomes involved, due to the low carbon content in the RA for the sample subjected to single annealing and that subjected to double annealing at 750°C, compared to the double annealing at 700°C, RA rapidly transforms to martensite during loading limiting the exploitation of the TRIP effect for enhanced ductility. However, as the true strain increases, although the CA-730–750 sample shows always a lower n , the rate of decrease slows down until the instability criterion is reached. It can be said that for the CA-730 sample, the transformation of RA is exhausted more rapidly, whereas in CA-730–750, RA remains active at higher strains. This may be attributed to the effect of double annealing

on the microstructure. This might be correlated to the impact of double annealing on the microstructure. On one hand, again a greater amount of martensite surrounding austenite may compensate the lower carbon content of the austenite improving the γ -mechanical stability delaying the TRIP effect. On the other hand, the development of a more heterogeneous microstructure—featuring austenite with varied sizes and morphologies (e.g., lath and globular)—due to the second annealing step, contributes to this behavior. This demonstrates that not only the volume fraction and carbon content of austenite, but also its size and morphology, play a crucial role in determining the mechanical response.

In contrast, when a double annealing is done at 700°C, the scenario is different: martensite is not present, and it does not affect the austenite hindering its transformation, and austenite is characterized by a higher carbon content respect to the previous conditions and higher in principle (Figure 8b). In this case, it seems that, in the current medium Mn steel, the TRIP effect contributes to the strain hardening more effectively. At very low strains, the specimen CA-730–700, the contribution to the work hardening of the material is mainly given by the ferritic matrix, then when the strain is sufficient to induce the TRIP effect, the transformation begins to contribute gradually until the instability is reached, in agreement with [79]. The work hardening is sustained though the UTS, which is considerably delayed, if compared to the other samples. Moreover, the development of different populations of austenite during the second annealing, and in particular of lamellar structures allows to sustain the n value at very high strains [77], ensuring the highest ductility and UTS \times TE product. Finally, possible changes in the mechanisms that operates in medium Mn steels in response to an external mechanical load, e.g., from TRIP to TWIP, or transition from strain to stress induced transformation [25], due to the heterogeneity of the microstructure may also affect the mechanical response. However, this cannot be determined with the techniques adopted in this study.

3.6 | Effect of Double Annealing on Fracture Behavior

To elucidate the influence of two-step annealing on fracture behavior, first a macroscopic analysis of fractured samples after single annealing at 730°C and double annealing at 700°C and 750°C was performed (see Figure 11a–c). The fracture path of the specimen CA-730 exhibits a flat surface morphology, without necking. While at high magnifications, Figure 11d, g, a brittle fracture was revealed, showing many brittle fracture characteristics: (i) secondary cracks (indicated by red arrows), (ii) quasi-cleavage fracture, and (iii) intergranular fracture.

After double annealing at 700°C the material showed significant necking, coupled with thinning and elongation, indicative of significant plastic deformation (Figure 11b), in agreement with the tensile curves shown in Figure 10. SEM observation shows delaminated regions (Figure 11e) populated with dimples, consistent with ductile fracture characteristics. The occurrence of delamination can be attributed to specific microstructural features, such as elongated prior austenite grain boundary (PAGB) and a laminated structure, induced by the cold deformation [80, 81], which are known to divert crack propagation paths,

FIGURE 11 | Cross-sectional light optical micrographs of the tensile specimens close to fracture surface of (a) CA-730, (b) CA-730–700, and (c) CA-730–750 sample. SEM overview of the fracture surface: (d) CA-730, (e) CA-730–700, and (f) CA-730–750 sample. Microscopic fracture morphologies (SEM) of (g) CA-730, (h) CA-730–700, and (i) CA-730–750 sample.

relieve triaxial stresses, dissipate fracture energy, and thereby enhance fracture toughness and ductility in medium Mn steels.

In contrast, when the material is reheated at 750°C for the second annealing step, the fracture surface exhibits again a flat morphology with minimal necking (Figure 11c) and a characteristic river pattern (Figure 11f), indicative of a brittle fracture mode. Only limited ductile shear lips are observed at the fracture edge. High-resolution images (Figure 11i) further confirm the predominance of brittle features, including secondary cracks, quasicleavage facets, and intergranular fracture.

This degradation in ductility and clear transition from ductile to brittle fracture with increasing annealing temperature and the superior performances compared to the single annealing are governed by the mechanical stability of RA and by the introduction of a martensitic phase in the microstructure. After a low temperature second annealing (CA-730–700), austenite is more stable compared to the single annealing or double annealing at 750°C, and undergoes strain-induced transformation, fails primarily via void nucleation and coalescence which is typical of ductile fracture. On the other hand, where RA is less stable, globular austenite grains transform into martensite through a stress-assisted mechanism during the early stages of deformation,

resulting in a sharp increase in the work hardening rate and flow stress. This accelerates the brittle fracture before significant plastic deformation occurs. However, with the techniques adopted in this study the real evolution of austenite cannot be detected (e.g., formation of ϵ -martensite).

4 | Conclusions

In this work, the effects of single and double annealing treatment on the microstructure evolution and mechanical behavior have been investigated in a 5 wt.% Mn-containing MMnS. The major findings are as follows:

- The microstructure after single annealing at 730°C mainly consists of ferrite, RA and martensite, with small amount of carbide precipitates. After the second soaking, both the samples exhibit a bimodal microstructure with a more globular and lath morphology of RA.
- Second annealing at 700°C leads to maximizing the final volume fraction of RA and its carbon content, while only a very small fraction of austenite was found after annealing at 750°C due to inadequate stabilization, which resulted in the formation of fresh martensite upon cooling.

- The development of multiple population of austenite with different degree of stability and size and bct/bcc phases due to the double annealing alter the mechanism that operates when external load is applied, leading to improved mechanical properties.
- The decrease of the double annealing temperature (750°C–700°C) leads to the distinct change of fracture mode from brittle to ductile type due to the optimum TRIP effect, achieved after the double annealing at 700°C. After single annealing (730°C) or double annealing at 750°C, the material exhibited intergranular fracture and minimal or no necking due to the less stable RA.

Author Contributions

Mattia Franceschi: conceptualization (equal); data curation (lead); formal analysis (lead); investigation (lead); software (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing review & editing (supporting). **Jose Antonio Jimenez:** data curation (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (supporting). **Carlos Garcia-Mateo:** conceptualization (lead); funding acquisition (equal); investigation (equal); project administration (equal); resources (equal); software (equal); writing – original draft (equal); writing – review & editing (supporting). **Radhakanta Rana:** conceptualization (lead); funding acquisition (lead); investigation (lead); project administration (lead); supervision (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review & editing (lead).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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